

TableS1 Diet for Mice

		Normal Diet	High fat diet	
Ingredients (g/kg)	Casein	200	200	
	L-cysteine	3	3	
	Corn starch	315	72.8	
	maltodextrin	35	100	
	sucrose	350	172.8	
	Crude fiber	50	50	
	soybean oil	25	25	
	lard oil	20	177.5	
	Mineral mix	35	35	
	Vitamin mix	10	10	
	choline chloride	2.5	2.5	
	Composition (kcal%)	Protein	20	20
		Carbohydrates	70	35
Fat		10	45	

Table S2 Primers for RT-qPCR

Primer Name	5'	序列	3'
qPCR-miNOS-F		CCAAAGTGACCTGAAAGAGGA	
qPCR-miNOS-R		TGCAGCTTGTCAGGGATTC	
qPCR-mIL-6-F		TGTTCTCTGGGAAATCGTGG	
qPCR-mIL-6-R		TGGTACTCCAGAAGACCAGA	
qPCR-mTNF α -F		CCCAAAGGGATGAGAAGTTCC	
qPCR-mTNF α -R		TTGAGATCCATGCCGTTGGC	
qPCR-m β -actin-F		CTGAGAGGGAAATCGTGCGT	
qPCR-m β -actin-R		CCACAGGATTCCATACCCAAGA	
qPCR-mClaudin 2-F		GGCTGTTAGGCACATCCAT	
qPCR-mClaudin 2-R		TGGCACCAACATAGGAACTC	
qPCR-mOccludin-F		ATCACTTTGCCATTGGAGG	
qPCR-mOccludin-R		ATTTATGATGAACAGCCCCC	
qPCR-mMuc2-F		ACAAAAACCCAGCAACAAG	
qPCR-mMuc2-R		GAGCAAGGGACTCTGGTCTG	
qPCR-mZO-1-F		TGCAATTCCAAATCCAAACC	
qPCR-mZO-1-R		AGAGACAAGATGTCCGCCAG	